

GEOPOLITICS OF NEW TECHNOLOGIES

1.	GEOPOLITICS OF NEW TECHNOLOGIES	2
1.1	AN OVERVIEW ON GEOPOLITICS OF NEW TECHNOLOGIES	2
1.2	THE EU POSITIONING.....	3
1.3	EMERGING TECHNOLOGIES AND DECLINING DEMOCRACIES?.....	5
2.	POLICIES FOR THE MONITORING THE EMERGENCE OF NEW TECHNOLOGIES	6
3.	LEGAL FRAMEWORK	7
3.1	NEW TECHNOLOGIES AND THE LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR INTELLIGENCE	7
3.2	LEGISLATIONS AND ETHICS: A <i>REALPOLITIK</i> APPROACH ON EMERGING TECHNOLOGIES.....	12

1. Geopolitics of new technologies

1.1 An overview on geopolitics of new technologies

The increasingly rapid evolution of technologies is reshaping power relations between states, but also between states and private actors. Those states that have invested heavily in technologies such as big data, 5G, artificial intelligence and quantum computing have already achieved advantages over other countries¹. Advantages that can be commercial if they are friendly countries, strategic advantages if they are potentially enemy countries. Today, and it will be more and more in the future, the sovereignty and the power of a State will be challenged by its ability to govern the technological landscape, and consequently to have power over 'data'².

Emerging technologies are having and will have a significant impact in both business/commerce and geopolitics. Of course, increased investment in certain sectors and technologies (5G, AI) will translate in the long run into profits for private companies and nation-states with theoretically positive employment on certain employment sectors. 5G is expected to generate \$13 trillion in global economic value and 22 million jobs by 2035, while the global artificial intelligence market is estimated to reach \$15 trillion by 2030³. These figures are prompting many states to embark on a race to compete in technology, especially to capture intellectual property related to new technologies. The United States, China, South Korea and Israel⁴ are some of the countries that are making major investments in these technologies, imposing their own standards and taking advantage of the private companies that already make up the technological landscape.

In the past, geopolitics were governed by oil⁵ and natural gas, and most private sector organizations did not have as much influence on the global economy. For some countries, commodities are still one of the few geopolitical levers they can rely on. In today's world, however, new geopolitical players are emerging: technology giants are geopolitical players and have become de facto global, supra-state and trans-national players⁶. In fact, these giant companies already have an impact on geopolitics: their strategies influence government investment in technologies and they are able to drive innovation. If on the one hand the research areas and new technologies developed by these large companies bring innovation, on the other hand this immense economic power turns into political power and their choices have important geopolitical consequences, against which voices are beginning to be raised by political representatives, even from the European Union itself. "We must impose democratic limits on the unbridled and uncontrolled political power of the internet giants", said Ursula Von der Leyen, president of the European Commission. "New technologies must never mean that others decide how we live our lives"⁷.

Since data is the main asset of a technological society, it is essential to regulate how it is collected, stored, transferred and used internationally. Data governance on a global scale is influenced by cultural shifts among states, and governments are aware that their sovereignty depends on their

¹ <https://www.ispionline.it/en/pubblicazione/data-new-power-geopolitics-30657>

² <https://www.forbes.com/sites/cognitiveworld/2020/02/06/unleashing-the-real-power-of-data/?sh=315d4119389d>

³ World Economic Forum https://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_The_Impact_of_5G_Report.pdf

⁴ Jean-Christophe Noël, "Israeli Cyberpower: The Unfinished Development of the Start-up Nation?", *Études de l'Ifri*, Ifri, November 2020.

⁵ <https://www.chathamhouse.org/2019/08/geopolitical-implications-future-oil-demand>

⁶ <https://www.ft.com/content/36f838c0-53c5-11ea-a1ef-da1721a0541e>

⁷ <https://www.pubaffairsbruxelles.eu/page/215/?cat=1>

ability to control information. Unfortunately, states' decision-making and regulatory processes are slower than technological evolution.

1.2 The EU positioning

The European Union member states and the EU as a whole are actually trying to enter the global technological competition as a fully developed actor able to respond to the challenges posed by both 'digital authoritarianism' and unrestricted US based big tech companies⁸.

Europe is also trying to catch up on the development of new technologies with respect to its American ally/competitor, while at the same time trying to overcome its dependence on raw materials⁹ and other sectors (for example, on China, seen both as a trading partner and as a potential enemy). Nevertheless, the competition between the US and China pushed the EU to aim at being an independent actor in the field on technology.

One of Europe's main challenges is that it has to juggle between the US (military allies) and China (trading partner) in terms of public policies on technologies, which are quite divergent. We must also remember that Europe is not always a unified actor, as member states sometimes act in asymmetrical motion with respect to US-China competition¹⁰.

In addition to the difficulty of the EU, as a hybrid political entity, to implement coherent strategies across all member states, it suffers from a paradox. As an economic power, the EU is on the same level as the US and China: it has a global influence on trade practices and flows as well as international standards. However, as a technological power, Europe's member states have more in common with Japan, South Korea, India, or the United Kingdom: while it hosts leading capabilities and world-class players in some areas (telecommunications, satellites and launchers, undersea cables, and supercomputers), it is fragmented and does not host large Internet platforms.

The EU, when member states have the political will, succeeds in being a leading international player, just think of its data protection policies. The EU has sought to protect individual and industrial data, unifying Europe's digital marketplace and fostering a thriving digital economy. Now it has become a global standard on individual data privacy, as illustrated by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)¹¹. One of the next goals, which some forward-thinking political figures are aiming for, is to curb the dominance of American 'big tech' companies in Europe, mainly due to their business and tax practices. Linked to this is also the ambition to support the development of Europe's digital infrastructure. Indeed, European companies now depend on American service providers for 90% of their data management¹². This brings risks in terms of third-party data access control, espionage, cyber threats and access security.

In the EU nowadays, there has been a growing political convergence on concerns about China. The EU has taken a tougher diplomatic stance towards China, although intra-European divisions remain¹³. Starting from 2019, the EU has officially considered China to be simultaneously a

⁸ <https://www.theatlantic.com/magazine/archive/2021/11/facebook-authoritarian-hostile-foreign-power/620168/>

⁹ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/MEMO_13_92

¹⁰ https://www.swp-berlin.org/publications/products/research_papers/2019RP04_lpt_orz_prt_web.pdf

¹¹ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/qanda_20_1166

¹² https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/swd-strategic-dependencies-capacities_en.pdf

¹³ T. Rühlig, 'Towards a More Principled European China Policy?', *Études de l'Ifri*, November 2020, pp. 23-27.

'negotiating partner, an economic competitor in the quest for technological leadership, and a systemic rival promoting alternative models of governance'¹⁴. Beyond the case of China, there is a growing shared understanding between the EU and the US of the dangers of politically using digital technologies for surveillance, manipulation, and repression of populations¹⁵.

At the same time, despite a cosmetic distancing on the 'political-cultural model' proposed by China, the EU is proposing and adapting bilateral partnerships around the world. One among all, precisely with China. Launched in 2018 and mirroring China's 'Belt and Road Initiative'¹⁶, the 'EU-Asia Connectivity Strategy'¹⁷ focuses on financing infrastructure projects, improving cross-border trade and flows (including data flows), and collaborating on research and innovation.

Table 1: Countries using US and Chinese technologies for surveillance activities¹⁸

Therefore, when it comes to technological issues, the EU is certainly an ally of the US, but obviously it does not disdain commercial agreements with other countries, even 'enemies' of the US. The problem is that we must not confuse relations regarding security and defense with those purely technological. Even when it takes a different form from defense, the technological relationship between EU and US is totally asymmetrical, exactly like the defense one¹⁹. Although the EU is a global standard, US companies are leading the way, and private and public investment in Europe remains far below US thresholds. US partners risk reproducing a defense-like situation, where Europeans' dependence sows division and limits their ability to determine their own course of action²⁰. As much as Europe, the United States, and other partners around the world share strategic goals, they are also economic competitors.

¹⁴ European Commission and HR/VP, 'EU-China – A Strategic Outlook', European Council, March 21-22, 2019.

¹⁵ <https://www.cigionline.org/articles/authoritarianism-has-been-reinvented-for-the-digital-age/>

¹⁶ OECD <https://www.oecd.org/finance/Chinas-Belt-and-Road-Initiative-in-the-global-trade-investment-and-finance-landscape.pdf>

¹⁷ European Parliament, Briefing 'Prospect for EU-Asia connectivity. The European way to connectivity', 06-04-2021, [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/EPRS_BRI\(2021\)690534](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/EPRS_BRI(2021)690534)

¹⁸ <https://carnegieendowment.org/2019/09/17/global-expansion-of-ai-surveillance-pub-79847>

¹⁹ <https://www.atlanticcouncil.org/blogs/geotech-cues/eu-us-tech-cooperation/>

²⁰ <https://carnegieeurope.eu/strategieurope/80503>

1.3 Emerging technologies and declining democracies?

Some scholars²¹ suggested that new technologies may be one of the concomitant causes of the decline of democracies. This section deals with the nexus between emerging technologies and democracy, as it seems crucial to remember that the way we approach new technologies will have primary consequences on our daily lives and on the political system in which we live²².

A first argument concerns the possibility of a democratic decline, alluding to the automation and digitalization of entire sectors with the consequent loss of millions of jobs, leading to strong social tensions, which many times in history have led to the emergence of authoritarian regimes²³.

A second argument links the decline of democracies to the expansion of information and communication technologies (ICT) and the transformation of the information landscape, mainly due to the 'business model' in the information world. In fact, the traditional media, in decline in print, have opted for inclusion in social networks and are increasingly profiting from advertising revenue (despite the declining number of subscriptions), leaving less and less room for quality journalism. The algorithmic workings and business model of social media influence whether voluntarily or involuntarily, locking each audience into distinct information bubbles²⁴. Instead, quality content becomes less and less accessible, reserved for those willing and able to pay. The lack of quality information accessible to all is one of the factors that inevitably leads to the democratic decline of societies²⁵.

From a certain point of view, it seems paradoxical that the very emergence of social media could be one of the causes of democratic decline. But, in fact, the web and social media are a double-edged sword. On the one hand, social media are a space of freedom of expression and potentially offer access to a multitude of information, which is why they are viewed with distrust by many regimes. On the other hand, the algorithmic operation of some of these platforms exacerbates polarization and misinformation²⁶. Some political parties, exploiting this side of technological progress, have managed to grab with targeted messages an important slice of voters, with a communication campaign never seen before. In short, while new technologies offer new possibilities for democratic participation, they also allow for powerful manipulation and surveillance by both private companies and state entities²⁷.

At the base of this ability to use social platforms there is what feeds them, that is personal data and their manipulation. It is attributed, depending on the case, to opposing political factions or foreign agents. The EU has responded, as we mentioned earlier, with legislation on data collection, transfer and use, despite strong opposition from American tech companies, as these regulations clash with

²¹ J. Anderson and L. Rainie, Many Tech Experts Say Digital Disruption Will Hurt Democracy, Pew Research Center, February 21, 2020, <https://www.pewresearch.org/internet/2020/02/21/many-tech-experts-say-digital-disruption-will-hurt-democracy/>.

²² <https://www.pewresearch.org/internet/2019/10/28/5-leading-concerns-about-the-future-of-digital-life/>

²³ <https://www.eesc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/resources/docs/qe-02-17-763-en-n.pdf>

²⁴ <https://edu.gcfglobal.org/en/digital-media-literacy/how-filter-bubbles-isolate-you/1/>

²⁵ Fukuyama, Francis. "The Future of History: Can Liberal Democracy Survive the Decline of the Middle Class?" *Foreign Affairs*, vol. 91, no. 1, Council on Foreign Relations, 2012, pp. 53–61, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/23217147>.

²⁶ <https://english.elpais.com/usa/2021-04-22/how-algorithmic-recommendations-can-push-internet-users-into-more-radical-views-and-opinions.html>

²⁷ <https://www.youngausint.org.au/post/how-social-media-algorithms-are-increasing-political-polarisation>

their business models. Technology companies justify their opposition with concerns that such regulations will erode innovation and competitiveness.

2. Policies for the monitoring the emergence of new technologies

The development of emerging technologies, regardless of the state or company that produces them, together with the increasing centrality of big data to the power of nation states, and consequently the possibility of concentrating economic, political and social power, are obviously constantly to be monitored. Data, finally, are now increasingly configured around politics, legislation, national interests and are solely outside the activities of private companies, becoming the center of geopolitical and diplomatic negotiations²⁸.

States, aware that the use of various online platforms can have a strong impact on democratic societies and institutions, free markets, freedom of expression and national security, have begun to address issues such as regulations concerning 'big tech' in order to protect rights while ensuring the possibility of innovation. Governments, including democratic ones, are also aiming to increase their surveillance and tracking capabilities. Although democratic governments do so primarily to ensure national security, some concerns about digital authoritarianism are coming to light. At the same time, there is a broader negotiation going on about what democratic internet governance should look like, with differences centered around security, data governance, the use of emerging technologies, and the rights of end users²⁹.

At the heart of European debates between companies, governments, law enforcement, and citizens about new technologies are issues of security, commerce, innovation, and human rights. In Europe, a number of trends are underway by states in dealing with existing and emerging technologies, which can be summarized in a few policies:

1. Development and increased focus on national and European infrastructures, with national and regional clouds
2. Priority to national and European technological capacity
3. Generation, sharing, use, ownership, and access of non-personal and personal data at the national and European level
4. Applicability of national and European legislation to the internet and digital technologies, in particular with regard to AI development, online platforms, and personal data governance
5. Influence in the standardization of bases relating to emerging technologies

With these changes, the individual's experience with digital and the level of surveillance possible may depend heavily on where they are and their nationality. Beyond the quality or type of infrastructure, hardware, or device, individuals may have access to different services and content depending on intermediary and content liability regimes, privacy requirements, and security standards. To some extent, this is already the case - as companies undertake restrictions based on geography when required by law - and companies treat European data differently to maintain GDPR compliance.

²⁸ <https://www.ispionline.it/en/pubblicazione/geopolitics-data-fraught-world-businesses-30649>

²⁹ [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2021/653636/EXPO_STU\(2021\)653636_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2021/653636/EXPO_STU(2021)653636_EN.pdf)

Data has become an essential resource for innovation, business and nations interests. As a result, various conflicts arise from different visions of how to use data, perceptions of ownership over it, where states have reasserted their role and politically reorganized the digital world with competing agendas, divergent national interests, and sometimes opposing understandings of the rights to be granted to their citizens.

3. Legal framework

3.1 New technologies and the legal framework for intelligence

In the European context, but in general as far as law is concerned, we certainly cannot say that there is a law on new technologies, since in truth law is eternally chasing after what already exists in reality, trying to intervene ex-post on something that already exists. There are, however, general principles to which intelligence must adhere in the exercise of its functions, established by the United Nations. Obviously, these principles also apply to the use of emerging technologies and most likely to those that have not yet been invented.

Table 2: International Standard of Good practices for the promotion of Human Rights and fundamental freedoms while countering terrorism³⁰

Mandate and legal basis	
Practice 1	Intelligence services play an important role in protecting national security and upholding the rule of law. Their main purpose is to collect, analyze and disseminate information that assists policymakers and other public entities in taking measures to protect national security. This includes the protection of the population and their human rights.
Practice 2	The mandates of intelligence services are narrowly and precisely defined in a publicly available law. Mandates are strictly limited to protecting legitimate national security interests as outlined in publicly available legislation or national security policies, and identify the threats to national security that intelligence services are tasked to address. If terrorism is included among these threats, it is defined in narrow and precise terms.
Practice 3	The powers and competences of intelligence services are clearly and exhaustively defined in national law. They are required to use these powers exclusively for the purposes for which they were given. In particular, any powers given to intelligence services for the purposes of counter-terrorism must be used exclusively for these purposes.
Practice 4	All intelligence services are constituted through, and operate under, publicly available laws that comply with the Constitution and international human rights law. Intelligence services can only undertake or be instructed to undertake activities that are prescribed by and in accordance with national law. The use of subsidiary regulations that are not publicly available is strictly limited, and such regulations are both authorized by and remain within the parameters of publicly available laws. Regulations that are not made public do not serve as the basis for any activities that restrict human rights.
Practice 5	Intelligence services are explicitly prohibited from undertaking any action that contravenes the Constitution or international human rights law. These prohibitions extend not only to the conduct of intelligence services on their national territory but also to their activities abroad.
Oversight institutions	
Practice 6	Intelligence services are overseen by a combination of internal, executive, parliamentary, judicial and specialized oversight institutions whose mandates and powers are based on publicly available law. An effective system of intelligence oversight includes at least one civilian institution that is independent of both the intelligence services and the executive. The combined remit of oversight institutions covers all aspects of the work of intelligence services, including their compliance with the law; the effectiveness and efficiency of their activities; their finances; and their administrative practices.

³⁰ <https://www2.ohchr.org/english/bodies/hrcouncil/docs/14session/a.hrc.14.46.pdf>

Practice 7	Oversight institutions have the power, resources and expertise to initiate and conduct their own investigations, as well as full and unhindered access to the information, officials and installations necessary to fulfil their mandates. Oversight institutions receive the full cooperation of intelligence services and law enforcement authorities in hearing witnesses, as well as obtaining documentation and other evidence.
Practice 8	Oversight institutions take all necessary measures to protect classified information and personal data to which they have access during the course of their work. Penalties are provided for the breach of these requirements by members of oversight institutions.
Complaints and effective remedy	
Practice 9	Any individual who believes that her or his rights have been infringed by an intelligence service is able to bring a complaint to a court or oversight institution, such as an ombudsman, human rights commissioner or national human rights institution. Individuals affected by the illegal actions of an intelligence service have recourse to an institution that can provide an effective remedy, including full reparation for the harm suffered.
Practice 10	The institutions responsible for addressing complaints and claims for effective remedy arising from the activities of intelligence services are independent of the intelligence services and the political executive. Such institutions have full and unhindered access to all relevant information, the necessary resources and expertise to conduct investigations, and the capacity to issue binding orders.
Impartiality and non-discrimination	
Practice 11	Intelligence services carry out their work in a manner that contributes to the promotion and protection of the human rights and fundamental freedoms of all individuals under the jurisdiction of the State. Intelligence services do not discriminate against individuals or groups on the grounds of their sex, race, color, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, or other status.
Practice 12	National law prohibits intelligence services from engaging in any political activities or from acting to promote or protect the interests of any particular political, religious, linguistic, ethnic, social or economic group.
Practice 13	Intelligence services are prohibited from using their powers to target lawful political activity or other lawful manifestations of the rights to freedom of association, peaceful assembly and expression.
State responsibility for intelligence services	
Practice 14	States are internationally responsible for the activities of their intelligence services and agents, and any private contractors they engage, regardless of where these activities take place and who the victim of internationally wrongful conduct is. Therefore, the executive power takes measures to ensure and exercise overall control of and responsibility for their intelligence services.
Individual responsibility and accountability	
Practice 15	Constitutional, statutory and international criminal law applies to members of intelligence services as much as it does to any other public official. Any exceptions allowing intelligence officials to take actions that would normally violate national law are strictly limited and clearly prescribed by law. These exceptions never allow the violation of peremptory norms of international law or of the human rights obligations of the State.
Practice 16	National laws provide for criminal, civil or other sanctions against any member, or individual acting on behalf of an intelligence service, who violates or orders an action that would violate national law or international human rights law. These laws also establish procedures to hold individuals to account for such violations.
Practice 17	Members of intelligence services are legally obliged to refuse superior orders that would violate national law or international human rights law. Appropriate protection is provided to members of intelligence services who refuse orders in such situations.
Practice 18	There are internal procedures in place for members of intelligence services to report wrongdoing. These are complemented by an independent body that has a mandate and access to the necessary information to fully investigate and take action to address wrongdoing when internal procedures have proved inadequate. Members of intelligence services who, acting in good faith, report wrongdoing are legally protected from any form of reprisal. These protections extend to disclosures made to the media or the public at large if they are made as a last resort and pertain to matters of significant public concern.
Professionalism	
Practice 19	Intelligence services and their oversight institutions take steps to foster an institutional culture of professionalism based on respect for the rule of law and human rights. In particular, intelligence

	services are responsible for training their members on relevant provisions of national and international law, including international human rights law.
Human rights safeguards	
Practice 20	<p>Any measures by intelligence services that restrict human rights and fundamental freedoms comply with the following criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - They are prescribed by publicly available law that complies with international human rights standards; - All such measures must be strictly necessary for an intelligence service to fulfil its legally prescribed mandate; - Measures taken must be proportionate to the objective. This requires that intelligence services select the measure that least restricts human rights, and take special care to minimize the adverse impact of any measures on the rights of individuals, including, in particular, persons who are not suspected of any wrongdoing; - No measure taken by intelligence services may violate peremptory norms of international law or the essence of any human right; - There is a clear and comprehensive system for the authorization, monitoring and oversight of the use of any measure that restricts human rights; - Individuals whose rights may have been restricted by intelligence services are able to address complaints to an independent institution and seek an effective remedy.
Intelligence collection	
Practice 21	National law outlines the types of collection measures available to intelligence services; the permissible objectives of intelligence collection; the categories of persons and activities which may be subject to intelligence collection; the threshold of suspicion required to justify the use of collection measures; the limitations on the duration for which collection measures may be used; and the procedures for authorizing, overseeing and reviewing the use of intelligence- collection measures.
Practice 22	Intelligence-collection measures that impose significant limitations on human rights are authorized and overseen by at least one institution that is external to and independent of the intelligence services. This institution has the power to order the revision, suspension or termination of such collection measures. Intelligence-collection measures that impose significant limitations on human rights are subject to a multilevel process of authorization that includes approval within intelligence services, by the political executive and by an institution that is independent of the intelligence services and the executive.
Management and use of personal data	
Practice 23	Publicly available law outlines the types of personal data that intelligence services may hold, and which criteria apply to the use, retention, deletion and disclosure of these data. Intelligence services are permitted to retain personal data that are strictly necessary for the purposes of fulfilling their mandate.
Practice 24	Intelligence services conduct regular assessments of the relevance and accuracy of the personal data that they hold. They are legally required to delete or update any information that is assessed to be inaccurate or no longer relevant to their mandate, the work of oversight institutions or possible legal proceedings.
Practice 25	An independent institution exists to oversee the use of personal data by intelligence services. This institution has access to all files held by the intelligence services and has the power to order the disclosure of information to individuals concerned, as well as the destruction of files or personal information contained therein.
Practice 26	Individuals have the possibility to request access to their personal data held by intelligence services. Individuals may exercise this right by addressing a request to a relevant authority or through an independent data-protection or oversight institution. Individuals have the right to rectify inaccuracies in their personal data. Any exceptions to these general rules are prescribed by law and strictly limited, proportionate and necessary for the fulfilment of the mandate of the intelligence service. It is incumbent upon the intelligence service to justify, to an independent oversight institution, any decision not to release personal information.
The use of powers of arrest and detention	
Practice 27	Intelligence services are not permitted to use powers of arrest and detention if they do not have a mandate to perform law enforcement functions. They are not given powers of arrest and detention if this duplicates powers held by law enforcement agencies that are mandated to address the same activities.

Practice 28	If intelligence services have powers of arrest and detention, they are based on publicly available law. The exercise of these powers is restricted to cases in which there is reasonable suspicion that an individual has committed or is about to commit a specific criminal offence. Intelligence services are not permitted to deprive persons of their liberty simply for the purpose of intelligence collection. The use of any powers and arrest and detention by intelligence services is subject to the same degree of oversight as applies to their use by law enforcement authorities, including judicial review of the lawfulness of any deprivation of liberty.
Practice 29	If intelligence services possess powers of arrest and detention, they comply with international human rights standards on the rights to liberty and fair trial, as well as the prohibition of torture and inhuman and degrading treatment. When exercising these powers, intelligence services comply with international standards set out in, inter alia, the Body of Principles for the Protection of All Persons under Any Form of Detention or Imprisonment, the Code of Conduct for Law Enforcement Officials and the Basic Principles on the Use of Force and Firearms by Law Enforcement Officials.
Practice 30	Intelligence services are not permitted to operate their own detention facilities or to make use of any unacknowledged detention facilities operated by third parties.
Intelligence sharing and cooperation	
Practice 31	Intelligence-sharing between intelligence agencies of the same State or with the authorities of a foreign State is based on national law that outlines clear parameters for intelligence exchange, including the conditions that must be met for information to be shared, the entities with which intelligence may be shared, and the safeguards that apply to exchanges of intelligence.
Practice 32	National law outlines the process for authorizing both the agreements upon which intelligence-sharing is based and the ad hoc sharing of intelligence. Executive approval is needed for any intelligence-sharing agreements with foreign entities, as well as for the sharing of intelligence that may have significant implications for human rights.
Practice 33	Before entering into an intelligence-sharing agreement or sharing intelligence on an ad hoc basis, intelligence services undertake an assessment of the counterpart's record on human rights and data protection, as well as the legal safeguards and institutional controls that govern the counterpart. Before handing over information, intelligence services make sure that any shared intelligence is relevant to the recipient's mandate, will be used in accordance with the conditions attached and will not be used for purposes that violate human rights.
Practice 34	Independent oversight institutions are able to examine intelligence-sharing arrangements and any information sent by intelligence services to foreign entities.
Practice 35	Intelligence services are explicitly prohibited from employing the assistance of foreign intelligence services in any way that results in the circumvention of national legal standards and institutional controls on their own activities. If States request foreign intelligence services to undertake activities on their behalf, they require these services to comply with the same legal standards that would apply if the activities were undertaken by their own intelligence services.

By law, all EU member states have in their legislation the regulation and organization of intelligence services, which are normally divided into two distinct bodies, one conducting civilian intelligence and the other military intelligence. In some EU member states, intelligence services are further divided into separate departments related to domestic security and foreign intelligence, or according to specific themes. In practice, however, due in part to the overlapping and blurring of activities and responsibilities, the line separating these bodies is increasingly ambiguous³¹. One need only think of the fact that certain digital techniques such as telephone interception, spyware, or geolocation of mobile devices are currently used by both military and civilian intelligence. The data collected are then sometimes uploaded to common platforms accessible to several services at the same time, even those not belonging to the services and participating more or less directly in certain operations, such as those against organized crime, corruption or terrorism.

³¹ European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, Surveillance by intelligence services: fundamental rights safeguards and remedies in the EU, volume 1 and volume 2 <https://fra.europa.eu/en/publication/2015/surveillance-intelligence-services-volume-i-member-states-legal-frameworks>

The issue of separation and the relationship between the different intelligence services and law enforcement is not merely formal: the separation between intelligence services and law enforcement is a safeguard against the concentration of powers in a single service and the consequent risk of arbitrary use of information. In fact, in most EU countries this division formally exists. At the same time, the increasing number of terrorist attacks in Europe in recent years has brought law enforcement and intelligence services closer together both within a nation and in international cooperation. As such, security professionals and even the public view joint investigations to dismantle terrorist cells and surveillance of suspects as a best practice. While this is positive as national and citizen security is improved, the lines between police and intelligence are in danger of becoming increasingly blurred. The *de jure* separation of intelligence services and the police does not imply that the exchange of information is *de jure* not possible. National legislation provides for how such data may be exchanged between different authorities, in accordance with the principles mentioned above, but does not prohibit it and indeed encourages it, especially in the fight against international terrorism.

With regard to the emergence of new technologies, technological developments and the need to respond to increasingly sophisticated and articulated threats, particularly international crime and terrorism, have decisively changed intelligence gathering techniques. Among EU member states, the general understanding and consensus is that the information 'of the future' is data, and intercepting a signal is simply a form of data collection. However, the mere collection of data by intelligence services is not universally accepted as the starting point of an interference with the right to privacy. US legislation, for example, places the start of an interference at a much later point in time than European legislation, where an interference does not start only when the intelligence services actually access and analyze the previously collected data, but also at the very moment of collection: this has to be taken into account with regard to interference and regulations in force regarding new technologies³².

Table 3: Different understanding of interference in the EU and US³³

³² European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, Surveillance by intelligence services: fundamental rights safeguards and remedies in the EU, volume 1 and volume 2 <https://fra.europa.eu/en/publication/2015/surveillance-intelligence-services-volume-i-member-states-legal-frameworks>

³³ *idem*

Beyond the differences on the principles governing intelligence, this does not mean that states act without precise frameworks in intelligence operations. Going into the details of the EU member states, all states have codified and legislated on the methods of surveillance used by intelligence services. Obviously there are great differences between the legislation of the various states both in terms of legal responsibility, allocation of powers, division between the various intelligence services etc. Intelligence legislation is constantly changing and trying to adapt to contemporary realities and challenges. In the last five years, many EU states have made changes to their intelligence legal systems.

Table 4: Laws and reforms introduced in EU Member States between 2017 and 2021³⁴

As we could see, there is no real existing legislation on new technologies. Existing legislation, national or international, concerns intelligence activities tout-court. Instead, there are a number of practices and recommendations about intelligence activities and the means that can be used that can also be applied when it comes to new technologies.

3.2 Legislations and ethics: a *realpolitik* approach on emerging technologies

Ethical concerns about emerging technologies are not among the topics discussed in depth in the intelligence community. New technologies, especially those that allow for big data collection, can be used for mass surveillance phenomena. Obviously, the question is not only that of the legality or potential of a new technology, but of the ethical justification for its use, such as safeguarding

³⁴ *idem*

national security, the lives of citizens, and the democratic order. In observing and using new technologies, one thing to pay attention to is the potential harm that could be done to a person in the event of surveillance.

It is important to mention that this topic is ambiguous, as it is difficult to define the ethical principles to be followed. Many researchers have tried to determine these principles, and many experts have studied and developed ethical frameworks that could be applied to the topic of surveillance and data collection and retention. For example, Ashely Deeks in her book³⁵ distinguishes six international standards that should be implemented to govern the form of surveillance of collected data.

1. Legality and notification of applicable standards
2. Limits on grounds for collecting or requesting data
3. Periodic review of surveillance authorization
4. Limits on data retention
5. Preference for internal action
6. Neutral oversight bodies

The above standards should have the following properties. First, international norms should provide a high degree of explicitness about what the norms cover and the ways in which actors understand them. These practices have previously been made explicit in the 'practices' in the UN document³⁶. The more precise and detailed the norms on surveillance and the technologies that can be used, the smaller the window for arbitrary official action.

Table 5: Accountability of the intelligence services³⁷

³⁵ Deeks Ashley, An International Legal Framework for Surveillance <https://www.ilsa.org/Jessup/Jessup16/Batch%202/DeeksLegalFramework.pdf>
³⁶ <https://www2.ohchr.org/english/bodies/hrcouncil/docs/14session/a.hrc.14.46.pdf>
³⁷ European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, *ibidem*

Regarding the emergence of new technologies and related legal and ethical issues, it may be interesting to propose a 'technoethical assessment'³⁸. A technoethical assessment (TEA) is an interdisciplinary, systems-based approach to assessing ethical dilemmas related to technology. TEAs aim to guide actions related to technology in an ethical direction by advancing knowledge of technologies and their effects; successful TEAs thus produce a shared understanding of knowledge, values, priorities, and other ethical aspects associated with technology. TEAs involve five key steps:

1. Evaluate the intended ends and possible side effects of the technology in order to discern its overall value (interest).
2. Compare the means and intended ends in terms of technical and non-technical (moral and social) aspects.
3. Reject those actions where the output (overall value) does not balance the input in terms of efficiency and fairness.
4. Consider perspectives from all stakeholder groups.
5. Examine technological relations at a variety of levels (e.g. biological, physical, psychological, social, and environmental)

In the end, what is meant by *realpolitik* about emerging technologies is not so much about accepting or rejecting certain technologies on the basis of ethical principles, but more about how to use them ethically, while respecting human rights and international and national laws governing intelligence services. The 'race for technology' is one from which there is no escape, and the emergence of new technologies guarantees superiority and, above all, security. The fundamental ethical discriminating element is the purpose for which a technology is used.

³⁸ Luppini, R. (2010). *Technoethics and the evolving knowledge society*. Hershey: Idea Group Publishing.